

EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS FOR SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY,
ENGINEERING AND MATHEMATICS

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1 ROLE/PURPOSE/OBJECTIVE OF THE DELIVERABLE

This Data Management Plan outlines how the research data collected was handled during and after the ER4STEM project. It describes the data set, how it was archived and preserved as well as how it will be shared. It also provides a description on how the data was treated before being uploaded in the Zenodo repository.

1.2 RELATIONSHIP TO OTHER ER4STEM DELIVERABLES

Research data was collected in work packages WP2 (Workshops and Curricula) and WP3 (Conferences and Competitions). The evaluation process is described in D6.1 (Evaluation Pre-Kit) and will be refined in D6.2. Deliverables D6.3, D6.4 and D6.5, which report the evaluation results with the data collected every year. The dissemination deliverables D8.2, D8.3 and D8.4, especially the report on scientific dissemination, are also closely linked to the data management plan.

1.3 STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

The Introduction states the purpose of the document and explains the type of information it contains. In chapter 3, the data collected during the project is described in detail. Chapter 4 deals with standards and metadata. Chapter 5 elaborates on which data was shared with whom and how and chapter 6 gives an overview on how the data was archived and stored during the project and afterwards. Chapter 7 describes how the data was treated and structure before being upload in the Zenodo repository.

2 INTRODUCTION

The ER4STEM Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines how the research data collected during the project was handled during and after the project.

It is structured as suggested in [1] and describes:

- the data set
- standards and metadata
- data sharing
- archiving and preservation

Throughout these sections, reference is made to data protection, ethics, the evaluation (WP6), publications and other forms of dissemination (WP7) as well as to the two main activities of data collection (WP2 and WP3).

The DMP was not a fixed document; it evolved and gained more precision and substance during the lifespan of the project. The first version of the DMP was delivered in project month 6 (M6). It was updated at month 35 (M35), before the final project review, to fine-tune it to the data generated and the uses identified by the project consortium. The data management was discussed in milestone MS2 in project month M4, where important decisions were taken for the first version of the DMP document. The DMP was discussed during each milestone reviews. Nevertheless, the biggest modification was done after the final milestone M35, when was introduced the treatment that must be done to the data before been uploaded to the Zenodo repository.

3 DATA SET

During the project research data was collected during the workshops and conferences. As part of work packages 2, 3 and 6 (WP2, WP3 & WP6), data is collected by partners from multiple sources at multiple sites. This data is quantitative and qualitative in nature and will be analysed from different perspectives for project development and scientific evaluation with results published in scientific conferences and journals.

Data was only collected following the informed consent, and in the case of minors, their parent or guardian.

3.1 DATA SET REFERENCE AND NAME

In this document data regarding the workshops conducted during the project by each of the partners will be referenced to as **workshops data set** and will include data of over 4000 children by the end of the project. A similar approach will be followed for the conference data, but with smaller numbers. This data set will be referenced to as **conferences data set**. Collected data is anonymized by using participant numbers (a randomly assigned number with partner code and project year). The participant key, which connects participant information to participant numbers, is the only document that contains personally sensitive material (name of the participant, age, parent or school name and contact information) and will not be shared outside of the partner organisation or with people in the partner organisation who do not require direct access to this information. The participant key will be stored securely according to Data Protection Laws and will not be removed from the partner organisations.

3.1.1 WORKSHOPS DATA SET

Since the data comes from multiple sources, the workshops data set had its own folder structure and following documents collected: Workshop information, pre-questionnaire, post-questionnaire, observations, interviews, artefacts of learning, tutor reflections, and encrypted sensitive data like videos and audio files. These files will be named using the following convention:

- For documents and templates created by the partner responsible for evaluation, Cardiff University, the data will be named after the organisation conducting the workshop or conference, a six-digit date of the workshop or conference, and the original file name. For example, PRIA_160416_ObservationSchedule.doc
- If multiple documents from the same organisation on the same date exist, identifiers will be added as appropriate to the data, i.e. TutorName or GroupName. For example, TUW_250616_Lara_TutorReflection.doc or TUW_250616_Julian_TutorReflection.doc
- If no Cardiff University template exists (typically for artefacts, audio and video), the name will state the organisation, the six-digit date, then the group name and data type. For example, AL_040216_RobotAddicts_AudioInterview
- The files will be stored in a folder structure as in Figure 1. The detailed process of planning and conducting the workshops is part of work package 2, their evaluation is part of work package 6 and already described in D6.1.

Figure 1: Workshop data folder structure

3.1.2 CONFERENCES DATA SET

The conferences data set is a compact and slightly adapted form of the workshops data set with fewer numbers of children and follows the same naming conventions.

In ECER2016, roughly 300 students were expected to be present, many of whom will have participated in preparatory workshops and thus will have already contributed to the workshops data set.

3.2 DATA SET DESCRIPTION

3.2.1 WORKSHOPS DATA SET

A detailed description of the evaluation method and the rationale behind it as well as detailed information on the collected data is provided in D6.1. In this document, the data set will be described as a summary.

The workshops data set includes following documents and information:

- Workshop Session Information (.doc)
 - Partner name
 - Dates (to-from)
 - Number of sessions
 - Location
 - Lead by
 - Other tutors/mentors
 - Age of students
 - Total number of students
 - Male/Female numbers
 - Group sizes
 - Total number of groups
 - How were the groups formed? Why?
 - Robotics kit

- Programming languages
 - Domain
 - Aims of workshop
 - Please include all relevant lesson materials (e.g. activity plan, each session/lesson plan, handouts, etc.) in the folder with this document
- Draw a scientist (writings translated into English, anonymised and digitalised .pdf)
 - Filled by the participants
 - To answer the question “are popular gender stereotypes about STEM held?”
- Questionnaires (anonymised and online or .xls)
 - Filled by the participants
 - Pre- and post-workshop questionnaires are used to collect largely quantitative data
 - Questions are split into personal information (age, gender and school), past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers
 - The post-workshop questionnaire also includes questions about the activities to help understand learners’ experiences of the workshop as a whole, what participants feel they have learned and what their future intentions are
 - Paper questionnaire answers to be entered into the online system
 - Free-text responses translated into English and entered into excel files
- Observations (translated into English, anonymised and digitalised .xls)
 - Observation protocol filled by the workshop facilitators or other observers
 - Video observation where possible to verify and expand upon observation notes, as well as sensitising data analysts to the context.
- Interviews (anonymised, transcribed and translated into English, .xls)
 - With focus groups, audio-recorded
 - Conducted to understand the experience of participants and their reasons for particular actions
- Artefacts of learning (translated into English where applicable, anonymised and digitalised .pdf)
 - Created by the participants
 - Identified as group work
- Participant reflections (translated into English, anonymised if applicable and digitalised if applicable, .xls)
 - Created individually and as a team
 - Either as a blog which acts as a reflection tool and a living artefact of the learning process, or as a guided reflection document
- Tutor reflections (translated into English, anonymised and digitalised, .xls)
 - Done by each of the tutors, mentors or workshop facilitators
 - The purpose is two-fold: 1) To document changes to workshop plans and the reasons for these; and 2) to document the evolution of activity plans between workshops.
- Sensitive data (audio and video recordings)
 - Audio recordings of interviews and any video recordings are encrypted and stored by the partner organisation and only encrypted video files are shared with evaluation partner Cardiff University for the purpose of analysis and archiving.

The data was collected during the workshops by partner organizations mostly from the workshop participants, children ages 7 to 18. Over 4000 participants in five European countries were planned for the whole duration of the project. The first year is regarded as a pilot year with approximately 1000 students participating in the pilot evaluation. Collected data was used to improve processes regarding the workshops as well as their evaluation. The data also informed the development of the framework. It was planned that the results of the

data analysis will be used in scientific publications, along with illustrative, fully anonymised extracts from the data set. Parts of the data set will be made available via open access (details in section 5).

3.2.2 CONFERENCES DATA SET

The conferences data set is a compact form of the workshops data set with fewer participants (in ECER2016 roughly 180 students participated). Collected data was used to improve processes regarding the conferences as well as their evaluation. The data will also inform the development of the framework. It is planned that the data will be used in scientific publications and parts of it made available via open access (details in section 5).

- Conference Session Information (.doc)
 - Partner name
 - Dates (to-from)
 - Number of sessions
 - Location
 - Lead by
 - Other tutors/mentors
 - Age of students
 - Total number of students
 - Male/Female numbers
 - Group sizes
 - Total number of groups
 - How were the groups formed? Why?
 - Robotics kit
 - Programming languages
 - Domain
 - Aims of conference
 - Please include all relevant materials (e.g. activity plan, each session/lesson plan, handouts, etc.) in the folder with this document
- Questionnaires (anonymised and online or .xls)
 - Filled by the participants
 - Used to collect largely quantitative data
 - Questions are split into personal information, existing attitudes and conference experience.
 - Paper questionnaire answers to be entered into the online system
 - Free-text responses translated into English and entered into excel files
- Observations (translated into English, anonymised and digitalised .xls)
 - Observation protocol filled by the conference facilitators or other observers
 - Video observation where possible to verify and expand upon observation notes, as well as sensitising data analysts to the context.
- Interviews (anonymised, transcribed and translated into English, .xls)
 - With focus groups, audio-recorded
 - Conducted to understand the experience of participants and their reasons for particular actions
- Artefacts of learning (translated into English where applicable, anonymised and digitalised .pdf)
 - Created by the participants
 - Identified as group work

- Participant reflections (translated into English, anonymised if applicable and digitalised if applicable, .xls)
 - Created individually and as a team
 - Either as a blog which acts as a reflection tool and a living artefact of the learning process, or as a guided reflection document
- Tutor reflections (translated into English, anonymised and digitalised, .xls)
 - Done by each of the tutors, mentors or workshop facilitators
 - The purpose is two-fold: 1) To document changes to workshop plans and the reasons for these; and 2) to document the evolution of activity plans between workshops.
- Sensitive data (audio and video recordings)
 - Audio recordings of interviews and any video recordings are encrypted and stored by the partner organisation and only encrypted video files are shared with evaluation partner Cardiff University for the purpose of analysis and archiving.

It was planned that the results of the data analysis was going to be used in scientific publications, along with illustrative, fully anonymised extracts from the data set. Parts of the data set will be made available via open access (details in section 5).

4 STANDARDS AND METADATA

The ER4STEM project followed the Ethical standards of the Cardiff School of Social Sciences and has ethical approval from the School of Social Sciences Research Ethics Committee. Besides following a rigorous evaluation protocol that included informed consent of children participating in ER4STEM activities as well as their legal guardian, the project will comply with national and EU legislation on Data Protection, particularly the European Data Protection Legislation (Directive 95/45/EC). All ER4STEM project collected data was anonymised before research analysis and any data that might make personal identification possible was protected with adequate measures. For details, please see section 6.

The main purpose of the data collection was the evaluation of the impact of the framework tools and activities on young people. The findings are available via the project deliverables and scientific publications. Workshops are an important part of the data collection, therefore metadata needed for the workshops was defined through the cooperation of work packages 2 and 6 (see section 4.1.1). This metadata or parts of it can be used as search parameters in an open access research repository that provides access to anonymised and processed research data (details of data sharing is in section 5). The metadata can also be made available in an appropriate form in the ER4STEM repository (work package 5).

4.1.1 WORKSHOPS METADATA

The workshops metadata includes the following information for each session:

- Partner name
- Dates (to-from)
- Number of sessions
- Location
- Lead by
- Other tutors/mentors
- Age of students
- Total number of students
- Male/Female numbers
- Group sizes
- Total number of groups
- How the groups were formed
- Robotics kit
- Programming languages
- Domain
- Aims of workshop

4.1.2 CONFERENCES METADATA

The conference metadata includes the following information:

- Partner name
- Dates (to-from)
- Number of sessions

- Location
- Lead by
- Other tutors/mentors
- Age of students
- Total number of students
- Male/Female numbers
- Group sizes
- Total number of groups
- How the groups were formed
- Robotics kit
- Programming languages
- Domain
- Aims of conference

5 DATA SHARING

All collected and anonymised data from the workshops and conferences as outlined in the sections before, were disseminated in one form or another. So far, these datasets do not include any information that the consortium considers worth protection for exploitation. All collected data were used for scientific evaluation and findings were published via scientific channels. Open access to these publications are available in the repository. It is important to highlight that these files correspond to the camera ready and not the files available on the publisher website. However, not all of the raw data can be made accessible to everyone for ethical reasons. Figure 2 outlines the decisions made by the consortium on how to handle data sharing at this point in time. In the following sections the decisions will be explained in further detail.

Figure 2: Data sharing plan

5.1.1 RESEARCH RESULTS AND DATA

As a European project under Horizon2020, the ER4STEM project consortium has declared its willingness to make all knowledge generated from the project publically available and provide open access to its scientific publications and research data [2]. Therefore, all deliverables of the project are open to public and accessible via the project's web page er4stem.com. The data sharing decisions was taken regarding these data sets only and need to be revised when other data sets are added.

5.1.2 DECISION TO EXPLOIT

The consortium agreed that the workshops data set does not include any information that should be protected for exploitation reasons. However, the project created an educational robotics repository (repository.er4stem.com), which will be sustainable after the project. Therefore, some data or knowledge generated or collected in the project might be identified as a unique selling point worthwhile of protection.

5.1.3 DECISION TO DISSEMINATE

The consortium decided to disseminate findings from the research data in scientific publications. The consortium also decided to use other non-scientific means to promote the project and its tools as well as the scientific findings. Scientix has already been proven to be a very competent collaboration partner in reaching one of the main stakeholders – STEM teachers – all over Europe.

The decision about dissemination channels was also affected by the cost factor (such as open access for scientific publications) and, although some budget was foreseen for open access publications, the consortium will prefer routes that minimize costs in order to make the research and knowledge generated by the project as diversely public as possible.

5.1.3.1 DELIVERABLES

Findings from the project research data were published in deliverables D6.3, D6.4 and D6.5.

5.1.3.2 CONFERENCE PRESENTATIONS AND PROCEEDINGS

Conference proceedings and books are very expensive for open access. Nevertheless, conference camera-ready versions can be shared under certain conditions. For example, IEEE and ACM allow authors to share camera-ready versions without problem, while Springer just allow authors to do the same after 12 months. Therefore, camera-ready versions of the articles written in the project and are available in the repository.

5.1.3.3 JOURNALS

Journal publications are open access and publicly available, linked through via the repository. It is also a common route to publish first findings in conferences, and then enhance them together with further findings in a journal paper which then can be open access. It was decided that the final scientific results that are going to be published in a journal paper could be gold access. Other journal papers will have green access for financial reasons (minimised cost, maximised dissemination).

5.1.4 RESEARCH DATA OPEN ACCESS REPOSITORY

The consortium committed to make all research data. However, the consortium also decided that the data and the persons having access to the research data should be restricted. In the following subsections the restrictions and the rationale behind these are explained.

5.1.4.1 RESTRICTED DATA

The research data collected during workshops and conferences were anonymised so that participants cannot be identified from the data. However, there is always the potential that individuals can be identified in audio, video and still images, even though they have been anonymised. Sharing this data with third parties would infringe data and child protection laws of the consortium countries. The consortium is not equipped with the competencies and time to take measures against this kind of identification, and even if it did so, it cannot guarantee that others could not apply countermeasures once in the possession of these materials. Thus the consortium decided not to share with third parties audio, video or still images which include any participant.

Even within the consortium, only the evaluation lead partner and partners who originally collected the data will have access to this data, which has been stored as described in section 6 of this document. The transcribed interviews and observation protocols may be made available via open access but only if they contain no identifying information.

The consortium decided that all research data needs to be “cleaned” and processed, for example, school names or other identifying information needs to be removed, and brought into a form that is useful for other researchers to validate or replicate research results, and also fitting into the open access repository metadata and search options. There needs to be a compromise between the chosen repository and its data formats and the research data processed for the repository. The consortium concluded that excel and word formats will be best formats in an open access repository.

As part of the process of gaining informed consent to collect data from participants, they must be informed of the storage, protection and use of the data. If the data is made accessible to others, the consent is not fully informed, as the consortium has limited means to identify for what purposes the data will be used and by whom. Therefore, the open access pilot is explained to participants and they are given the opportunity to opt out of open access, thus data from participants who have opted out of open access pilot will not be made accessible. In addition, the consortium will limit the access to data to researchers who confirm their compliance with the same ethical obligations stated in the informed consent process.

5.1.4.2 RESTRICTED ACCESS

In order to ensure that the research data is used by third parties as explained to the participants with the informed consents, access to the data needs to be restricted. The consortium needs to know who is accessing the database and for what purpose. Criteria for access will include membership of a research institution based in Europe and they must submit a plan outlining how they will use the data (research questions and analysis approach) which will be reviewed before any decision to grant access.

The time frame of access is also part of the restriction. The research data cannot be made accessible before scientific publication. It therefore needs to be decided how long after publication it could be useful for other researchers to have access to the research data, this could range from one year post-publication to five years after the project.

Each person who would be interested to have access to any data set must make a request to the project team, stating the reason for access to the data and how it will be used. Also the following are the condition of use:

- The project team must be informed of intended publications arising from analysis of the data.

- The data set must be used in any publications with acknowledgement given to the authors and ER4STEM project.
- The dataset must not be used for commercial purposes and cannot be shared with others without express written consent from the project team.

On the other hand, the internal procedure to process a new request is the following: whoever picks up the request for access, must inform the partner leads, who are Markus Vincze(TU Wien), Wilfried Lepuschitz (PRIA), Ivo Gueorguiev (ESICEE), Angele Giuliano (AL), Chronis Kynigos (UoA) and Carina Girvan (CU). This should include information about the person and their stated reasons for wanting access to the data. The partner who collected the data can veto any access requests - allow 1 calendar month for this. If there are no causes for concern, access is granted.

6 ARCHIVING AND PRESERVATION

All research data will be stored until 2023. Partners also will need to archive personal data about the participants (the participant key) in a separate location, so that participants are able to use their right of withdrawing from the research anytime. The project partners will comply with national and EU legislation on Data Protection, particularly the European Data Protection Legislation (Directive 95/45/EC).

Each project partner will store the research data that is collected by that partner anonymously on a password protected server. Videos and audio files (and files where participant can be recognized) will only be stored in an encrypted drive and shared encrypted. Cardiff University will store all the data in the same way for all partners to ensure archiving in two separate locations. TU Wien will save Cardiff University research data for the same reason. The consortium has agreed to use the software VeraCrypt for encryption. For the needs of ER4STEM VeraCrypt provides sufficient security. It is open source, can be used on different systems (Windows, OS, Linux), it originates in Europe, is maintained by a French company, and is free of charge.

Software: <https://veracrypt.codeplex.com/>

Tutorial: <https://veracrypt.codeplex.com/wikipage?title=Beginner%27s%20Tutorial>

The website er4stem.com, which stores all publications of the project for public access, and the ER4STEM repository, which will store different tools and plans developed in the project, will be available at least five years after the project. Details about the research data open access repository can be found in section 5.1.5.

7 UPLOADING DATA SETS IN ZENODO

Each partner will upload all the data sets created during the project in the repository Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>). This repository was selected because it is located in Europe and it complies with all the requirements demanded by Cardiff University, which was the institution with the strictest and specific requirements between all partners. The following sections provide important information that must be considered by each partner while they are uploading the data sets. A guidance is provided in Annex A: Guidance for Open Access Data Sets.

7.1 FOLDER STRUCTURE

The following is the structure of each one of the data sets:

- Country + Partner initials
 - Year X
 - Workshop + 3 digit code
 - Artefacts of learning
 - (Use sub-folders as appropriate)
 - Draw-a-scientist
 - Interviews
 - Observation notes
 - Questionnaires
 - Reflections
 - Tutor
 - Student

At the Country + Partner level, a **README.txt** file is included with the following information:

- Language used to ask questions:
- Note to say that answers were translated from X language to English

Names of schools, tutors and teachers should be **REMOVED** from any file. This is due to ensure the anonymity.

7.2 CLEANING DATA

Each partner has to follow the next steps to all the data generated by them:

Step 1: Remove any participant for whom there is no consent to make their data open access.

Step 2: Anonymise all data

- No names of students, teachers, tutors or schools in ANY data (replace with student ID as appropriate)
- No images of children, adults or school names (blurred or not these must NOT be included)
- No audio or video recordings
- No sensitive data

7.3 ADDITIONAL CONSIDERATIONS

The following are additional considerations that each partner must take when they are uploading any data set on Zenodo:

- **Authors:** List all members of your team that did data collection and then add the following:

- George Sharkov; European Software Institute – Center Eastern Europe
 - Wilfried Lepuschitz; Practical Robotics Institute Austria
 - Angele Giuliano; AcrossLimits
 - Chronis Kynigos; Kapodistrian University of Athens
 - Carina Girvan; Cardiff University
 - Markus Vincze; Technical University Wein
- **Description:** “This dataset was collected as part of the Educational Robotics for STEM (ER4STEM) project, funded by the European Commission’s Horizon 2020 programme, grant agreement No. 665792. The dataset includes quantitative and qualitative data collected over 3 years of robotics workshops held in XXX (Replaces with the correct text). Only data with informed consent to be shared via an open access repository is included. Only anonymised data is included and some data is excluded to protect vulnerable participants.”
 - **Keywords:** Educational robotics; ER4STEM; K-12; Science; Technology; Engineering; Mathematics; STEM; Quantitative; Qualitative
 - **Licence:** Select - Restricted Access. The following text to conditions: “Access to this dataset is restricted. Access requests must be made to the project team, stating the reason for access to the data and how it will be used. Conditions for use: The project team must be informed of intended publications arising from analysis of the data. The dataset do must be used in any publications with acknowledgement given to the authors and ER4STEM project. The dataset must not be used for commercial purposes and cannot be shared with others without express written consent from the project team.
 - **Funding:** 665792 OR ER4STEM

8 CONCLUSION / OUTLOOK

The ER4STEM DMP Version 2.0 outlines how the research data collected during the project was handled during and after the project. The document was reviewed at each milestone meeting and adapted as the project progresses. Also, it provides instructions on how to update the data sets on Zenodo, which is the repository selected to store the data created from the project.

9 GLOSSARY / ABBREVIATIONS

EC	European Commission
ER4STEM	Educational Robotics for STEM
DMP	Data Management Plan
REA	Research Executive Agency
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics

10 BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] European Commission. Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020. Version 2.0. 30 October 2015
- [2] European Commission. Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020. Version 2.0. 30 October 2015

11 ANNEX A: GUIDANCE FOR OPEN ACCESS DATA SETS

11.1 FOLDER STRUCTURE

- Country + Partner initials
 - Year X
 - Workshop + 3 digit code
 - Artefacts of learning
 - (Use sub-folders as appropriate)
 - Draw-a-scientist
 - Interviews
 - Observation notes
 - Questionnaires
 - Reflections
 - Tutor
 - Student

At the Country + Partner level, please include a READ ME .txt file with the following information:

- Language used to ask questions:
- Note to say that answers were translated from X language to English

Year 1 workshops will need to include the workshop information document with names of schools, tutors and teachers REMOVED.

11.2 CLEANING DATA:

All data:

Step 1: Remove any participant for whom there is no consent to make their data open access.

Step 2: Anonymise all data

- No names of students, teachers, tutors or schools in ANY data (replace with student ID as appropriate)
- No images of children, adults or school names (blurred or not these must NOT be included)
- No audio or video recordings
- No sensitive data

Year 2 & 3 questionnaires:

Note: Make sure you are using the most recent version of the files (corrected by Ivo & Julian)

The process includes steps as follows:

1. Open the file and go to Workshop Information sheet. Select all cells in the “Workshop Information” sheet by pressing Ctrl + A buttons and then while keeping the Ctrl button release A button and press it

again. In this way all the cells are selected.

Communication	no	
Creativity	yes	P
Critical thinking	yes	P
Evidence of learning	yes	II

Workshop Information | Group Information Session 1 | Group Information Session 2 | Gr

- Copy the cells by pressing Ctrl+C buttons
- Paste the cells using Paste special -> Paste Values. You can choose one of the methods illustrated below:

Note: University of Athens might need to use the methods described in step 1, 2 and 3 in order to remove formulas from "Pre-Questionnaire *", "Post-Questionnaire *" sheets

- Check if the formulas were released with values by selecting cell B47. You should see only a number in this cell but not formula:

- If you do not see "AGREGATED_DATA", then unhide "AGREGATED DATA" sheet by pressing right mouse button to any sheet name (in bottom of the screen)

- Delete "AGREGATED_DATA" sheet by pressing right mouse button to the AGREGATED_DATA sheet name at the bottom of the screen

7. Delete all hidden sheets (if any) using steps 5 and 6!
8. Delete “Change management” sheet by pressing right mouse button to the “Change management” sheet name at the bottom of the screen (same method as you did in step 6)
9. Delete all empty or not used sheets. (same method as you did in step 6)
10. **Anonymising:**
 - a. Clear the data of all students, who do not allow open data sharing.
 - b. On the group information sheets, code as 0 and remove the gender for any who do not allow open data sharing
 - c. Remove the names of the school, teacher & tutors on the Workshop Information Sheet

Year 1 questionnaires:

- Anonymise as above.

11.3 UPLOADING:

Log into Zenodo using the instructions sent by Julian

Upload steps:

1. Click ‘Upload’

2. Choose ‘New Upload’
3. Add a SINGLE zipped file of all data from the partner (see folder structure above). Max size 50GB (if you exceed this email Carina)

New upload

Instructions: (i) Upload minimum one file or fill-in required fields (marked with a red star). (ii) Press "Save" to save your upload for editing later. (iii) When ready, press "Publish" to finalize and make your upload public.

- In Communities, select European Commission Funded Research (start typing and it will auto fill)

Once selected it should appear like this:

- Upload type: Select '**Dataset**'

- Digital Object Identifier: Leave blank
- Date: Leave as default (today's date)
- Title: Horizon 2020 ER4STEM workshop data Year 1-3 [Country name]
- Authors:

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

- List all members of your team that did data collection and then add the following:
 - George Sharkov; European Software Institute – Center Eastern Europe
 - Wilfried Lepuschitz; Practical Robotics Institute Austria
 - Angele Giuliano; AcrossLimits
 - Chronis Kynigos; Kapodistrian University of Athens
 - Carina Girvan; Cardiff University
 - Markus Vincze; Technical University Wien

required ▼

Digital Object Identifier e.g. 10.1234/foo.bar

Optional. Did your publisher already assign a DOI to your upload? If not, leave the field empty and we will register a new DOI for you. A DOI allows others to easily and unambiguously cite your upload. Please note that it is NOT possible to edit a Zenodo DOI once it has been registered by us, while it is always possible to edit a custom DOI.

Reserve DOI

Publication date * 2018-09-12

Required. Format: YYYY-MM-DD. In case your upload was already published elsewhere, please use the date of first publication.

Title * [Empty field]

Required.

Authors *

Family name, given names

Affiliation

ORCID (e.g.: 0000-0002-1825-0097)
✕

Optional.

[+ Add another author](#)

10. Description: (edit the sentence highlighted as necessary – note this was written for the UK) “This dataset was collected as part of the Educational Robotics for STEM (ER4STEM) project, funded by the European Commission’s Horizon 2020 programme, grant agreement No. 665792. **The dataset includes quantitative and qualitative data collected over 3 years of robotics workshops held in schools in the UK.** Only data with informed consent to be shared via an open access repository is included. Only anonymised data is included and some data is excluded to protect vulnerable participants.”

11. Version: Leave blank

12. Language: ‘English’

13. Keywords: Each of these needs to be inputted separately - Educational robotics; ER4STEM; K-12; Science; Technology; Engineering; Mathematics; STEM; Quantitative; Qualitative

14. Additional notes: Leave blank

Description *

Rich text editor toolbar: Bold (B), Italic (I), Strikethrough (ABC), Subscript (x₂), Superscript (x²), Link, Unlink, Bulleted List, Numbered List, Decrease Indent, Increase Indent, Quote, Table, Undo, Redo, Text Color, Background Color, Source, Refresh.

Required.

Version

Optional. Mostly relevant for software and dataset uploads. Any string will be accepted, but semantically-versioned tag is recommended. See semver.org for more information on semantic versioning.

Language

Optional. Primary language of the record. Start by typing the language's common name in English, or its ISO 639 code (two or three-letter code). See [ISO 639 language codes list](#) for more information.

Keywords

[+ Add another keyword](#)

Additional notes

Optional.

15. Licence:

- a. Select - Restricted Access
- b. Add the following text to conditions: "Access to this dataset is restricted. Access requests must be made to the project team, stating the reason for access to the data and how it will be used. Conditions for use: The project team must be informed of intended publications arising from analysis of the data. The dataset doi must be used in any publications with acknowledgement given to the authors and ER4STEM project. The dataset must not be used for commercial purposes and cannot be shared with others without express written consent from the project team.

License required ▾

Access right *

- Open Access
- Embargoed Access
- Restricted Access
- Closed Access

Required. Open access uploads have considerably higher visibility on Zenodo.

Conditions

Rich text editor toolbar: Bold, Italic, Strikethrough, Subscript, Superscript, Link, Unlink, Bulleted List, Numbered List, Indent, Outdent, Quote, Table, Undo, Redo, Source, Refresh.

Specify the conditions under which you grant users access to the files in your upload. User requesting access will be asked to justify how they fulfil the conditions. Based on the justification, you decide who to grant/deny access. You are not allowed to charge users for granting access to data hosted on Zenodo.

16. Funding: Add the grant agreement number: 665792 OR ER4STEM in the yellow highlighted box.

Funding recommended ▾

Zenodo is integrated into reporting lines for research funded by the European Commission via [OpenAIRE](#). Specify grants which have funded your research, and we will let your funding agency know!

Grants

Optional. OpenAIRE-supported projects only. For other funding acknowledgements, please use the *Additional Notes* field.
Note: a human Zenodo curator will need to validate your upload - you may experience a delay before it is available in OpenAIRE.

[+ Add another grant](#)

The box should then autofill:

Funding recommended ▾

Zenodo is integrated into reporting lines for research funded by the European Commission via [OpenAIRE](#). Specify grants which have funded your research, and we will let your funding agency know!

Grants

Optional. OpenAIRE-supported projects only. For other funding acknowledgements, please use the *Additional Notes* field.
Note: a human Zenodo curator will need to validate your upload - you may experience a delay before it is available in OpenAIRE.

[+ Add another grant](#)

17. The following can be left empty:

Related/alternate identifiers	recommended >
Contributors	optional >
References	optional >
Journal	optional >
Conference	optional >
Book/Report/Chapter	optional >
Thesis	optional >
Subjects	optional >
<input type="button" value="Delete"/>	<input type="button" value="Save"/> <input type="button" value="Publish"/>

18. Choose to Publish by clicking the blue 'Publish' button. If it is unavailable, a required field has not been completed.

19. If you are unsure of anything, click 'Save' and contact Carina.

